

BASIC RULES OF THE DEFENSE DOCTRINE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This article comprehensively analyzes the fundamental provisions, strategic directions and functional role of the Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan in ensuring state security. The article scientifically and conceptually substantiates the principles of multi-vector neutrality of the state, such as non-alignment with blocs, non-deployment of foreign military bases on its territory, and medium-term programs for the development of the military-economic, defense-industrial complex.

Keywords: Defense Doctrine, Armed Forces, sole leadership, Supreme Commander-in-Chief, hybrid threats, cyberspace, cross-border crime, military-political blocs, neutrality, defense-industrial complex, unification.

In the first quarter of the 21st century, the global geopolitical architecture has undergone a serious transformation: traditional wars have been replaced by conflicts of a networked, asymmetric and hybrid nature. In such complex conditions, the Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan serves as an international legal and military-strategic guarantee of protecting the sovereignty and territorial integrity of the country.

The main principle of the structure of the Armed Forces is to replenish the composition so that it is not numerous, but mobile, well-armed with modern weapons and combat equipment, capable of reliably ensuring state security.

The Armed Forces organize and carry out their activities on the basis of:

- the rule of law; centralized management and leadership;
- constant combat and mobilization readiness;
- universal military obligation of citizens;
- creation of a collective security system;
- ensuring social protection of military personnel and their family members.

In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Defense", all orders for defense needs are encouraged in the form of tax reductions or exemptions, loans and other benefits.

The powers of the President include general or partial mobilization, declaration of a state of war in the event of an armed attack on the republic; adoption of regulatory documents and termination of their activities during wartime; coordination of the activities of state bodies in the field of defense; holding discussions on military issues and signing international treaties; training and appointment of persons from among the ranks of high-ranking officers to military positions; awarding them military and special ranks.

I. General Provisions

The Republic of Uzbekistan confirms the defensive nature of the Doctrine. The Republic of Uzbekistan does not consider any state to be its enemy and builds relations with all countries on the basis of the priority of the country's national interests and taking into account the

generally recognized principles and norms of international law, mutual benefit, equality and non-interference in the internal affairs of other states, the resolution of all disputes by peaceful means and negotiations, and the recognition of the inviolability and immutability of established interstate borders.

II. Military-political aspects of the doctrine.

The main threats to national security in the military sphere are:

military conflicts with the risk of military action moving to the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Demonstrative increase in the number of troops near the State border of the Republic of Uzbekistan in such a way as to disrupt the balance of power in the region and to indicate preparations for military aggression against the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Encroachment on the sovereignty and territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan; the organization, training and arming of illegal armed formations for direct deployment to the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan or to the border regions of neighboring states;

cross-border and international organized criminal activities related to drug trafficking, smuggling of weapons, ammunition, toxic and explosive substances, and other means used to carry out subversive and terrorist activities;

ideological and psychological actions in the information and communication space directed against the sovereignty, independence, territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan and threatening the peaceful life of the population.

The main goals of the defense policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan are:

protection of independence, sovereignty, territorial integrity and constitutional order;

ensuring the military security of the state;

strengthening international and regional cooperation, security, stability and good neighborliness in Central Asia;

systematically developing the state's military organization, maintaining it in a state of readiness for armed defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The defense policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on the following principles:

non-use of military force against other states, except in cases of prevention and repelling military aggression;

non-division of security, inadmissibility of strengthening one's own security at the expense of the security of other states;

non-interference in the internal affairs of other states, peaceful resolution of possible conflicts;

non-participation in military-political blocs, retaining the right to withdraw from any interstate structure if it is transformed into a military-political bloc;

sufficient level of defense;

military construction should be consistent with the nature of modern military conflicts;

Refusal to produce, acquire, store, distribute and deploy nuclear and other types of weapons of mass destruction;

Commitment to the principles of the Treaty on a Nuclear-Weapon-Free Zone in Central Asia;

Non-admission to the deployment of foreign military bases and facilities on its territory;

Non-participation of the Armed Forces in peacekeeping operations and military conflicts abroad;

Reliance on the spiritual and moral values and unique cultural civilization of the people.

III. Military-strategic aspects of the doctrine

The main directions of the development of the Armed Forces are:

Improvement of the organization, structure and composition of the troops and military formations of the Armed Forces, taking into account national and foreign experience of military construction;

combat and mobilization readiness of the troops, planning and organizing operational, combat, spiritual-educational and psychological training of the troops, as well as improving the systems for training the trained mobilization reserve;

optimization of management bodies at all levels, formation of unified protected information and communication systems for commanding troops and weapons;

further development of structures for operational (combat) support of operations and tactical actions of the troops;

improving the quality of military education and training, retraining and advanced training of national military-scientific and pedagogical personnel.

IV. Military-economic aspects of the doctrine

The main tasks of military-economic support of the country's defense are:

improvement of the legislation regulating the placement of state orders for the supply and production of military and dual-purpose products, the performance of work and the provision of services for the needs of the country's defense;

timely and rational implementation of programs for the development of economic sectors for the production of dual-purpose products, as well as programs for providing the Armed Forces with modernized and promising models of weapons, military and special equipment in an economically and financially sound manner;

optimization of the costs of financial and material resources directed to ensuring military security, increasing the efficiency of their use based on the interconnected, harmonious development of all components of the state military organization;

creation of economic and financial conditions for the development and production of unified, protected information and communication systems for commanding troops and weapons, reconnaissance, warning, radio-electronic warfare systems, as well as high-precision targeting means;

development of the scientific, technical, technological and production base of the country, the Armed Forces and the military infrastructure;

harmonization of the civilian and military sectors of the economy and coordination of the military-economic activities of the state in the interests of ensuring its military security;

raising the standard of living of military personnel and their family members, implementing social guarantees established by law;

improving the country's mobilization readiness and preparedness systems;

implementing mutually beneficial international military and military-technical cooperation.

The main directions of development of the country's defense industry complex are:

implementation of medium-term programs providing for a complex of measures to create favorable conditions for the effective operation of defense industry enterprises, institutions and organizations;

introduction of a state system for the formation and conduct of scientific research and experimental design work in the military-technical direction;

establishment of enterprises with foreign investment and establishment of cooperative relations with interested foreign partners;

mastering highly demanded technologies in the field of creation, production, repair and modernization of military-purpose products;

training, retraining and upgrading of managerial personnel, scientific, engineering and technical personnel and workers, introduction of incentive social measures to increase the attractiveness of labor activity in the military sector of the economy.

In conclusion, the Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the laws regulating state activities in preparing the country for defense, organizing actions against aggression against the military security of the republic, and the use of the Armed Forces to protect the vital interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Republic of Uzbekistan, declaring the essence of its Defense Doctrine, guarantees strict compliance with all international obligations arising from the Charter of the United Nations, the Final Act signed in Helsinki, the Stockholm Conference Document, bilateral, multilateral treaties and agreements, and generally recognized norms of international legal instruments.

The reliable defense capability of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the high combat capability of the Armed Forces are ensured by the development of economic, military-technical and scientific power, the unity of the people of Uzbekistan and the patriotic upbringing of each citizen.

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